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HUMAN RIGHTS AND TERRORISM: A CRITICAL EXAMINATION OF BOKO HARAM'S IMPACT IN NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA

Musa Alkali Lawan,*Joseph I. Aremo,Muhammad Shettima,***And Abdullah
Usman******

**Departments of Public Law, Faculty of Law, University of Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria*

***Faculty of Law, Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, Ondo State, Nigeria*

****Department of Sharia, Faculty of Law, University of Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria*

*****Department of Sharia and Civil Law, Mohammed Goni Collage of Legal, Educational and Islamic Studies,
Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria.*

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

MUSA ALKALI LAWAN, PhD

Departments of Public Law,

Faculty of Law,

University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri

Borno State Nigeria

Email; musaalkalilawan@gmail.com,

[+2347060757000](tel:+2347060757000)

ABSTRACT

This paper critically examines the impact of Boko Haram's terrorism on human rights in Northeastern Nigeria. It explores how both Boko Haram's violent activities and the Nigerian government's counterterrorism measures have led to widespread human rights violations. Using securitization theory and the frameworks on International Humanitarian Law and International Human Rights Law as well domestic legislation, the paper analyses issues such as extrajudicial killings, torture, rape, sexual violence, forced marriage, arrests and unlawful detentions and suppression of civil liberties. It argues that the dual crises of terrorism and counterterrorism have undermined human rights protection and calls for a right-based approach that balances security imperatives with the rule of law and accountability.

KEYWORDS: Human Rights, Terrorism, Boko Haram, Counterterrorism, Impact in Northeastern, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the intersection of terrorism and human rights has become a pressing concern for policymakers, human rights advocates, and scholars alike. Nowhere is this intersection more violently expressed than in the insurgency of *Boko Haram* in northeastern Nigeria and parts of the Lake Chad Basin. As a non-state armed group with an extreme ideological stance, *Boko Haram* has waged a brutal campaign against the Nigerian state and civilian populations, targeting schools, religious centres, villages, and security forces. The group's tactics ranging from mass abductions to suicide bombings have led to widespread violations of fundamental human rights, including the right to life, education, freedom of religion, and personal security.

At the same time, the Nigerian government's counterterrorism strategies, while aimed at restoring national security, have themselves raised serious human rights concerns. Reports of extra-judicial killings, arbitrary detentions, enforced disappearances, and abuse of internally displaced persons (IDPs) have emerged, highlighting the complex dilemma of balancing national security with the human rights. With this dual reality terrorism induced suffering on one hand, and state sanctioned abuse on the other hand, organizations such as Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch have documented serious human rights violations by the security agencies. This raises critical questions about accountability, the rule of law, and the protection of civilians in conflict settings.

This paper seeks to critically examine the intersection between terrorism and human rights violation through the lens of securitization theory of the *Boko Haram* insurgency in Northeastern Nigeria with the aims to analyze the nature and extent of human rights violations committed by *Boko Haram*; investigate the Nigerian government's counterterrorism strategies and their compliance with international human rights norms; evaluate the impact of the conflict on vulnerable populations, particularly women, children, and IDPs and to propose policy recommendations for a more human rights compliance approach to addressing terrorism.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

- **Securitization Theory and Conceptual Framework**

This paper is situated at the intersection of human rights theory, terrorism studies, and international legal frameworks, providing a foundation for understanding how violent non-state actors and state responses interact with the rights and protections of civilians in conflict zones. Several conceptual and legal tools are used to guide the analysis of *Boko Haram's* activities and the Nigerian government's counterterrorism efforts.

- **Conceptualizing Human Rights in Conflict Contexts**

Human rights are generally understood as the inalienable rights and freedoms to which all individuals are entitled, regardless of status, nationality, or location. Human rights according to United Nations are rights inherent to all human beings, irrespective of

nationality, race, sex, residency, religion, language or any other status.²⁴ These rights are said to be ‘all interrelated, interdependent and indivisible’.²⁵ Henkin argues that Human Rights are not the equivalent of justice or the good society or even democracy though there is a relationship.²⁶ Human Rights suggest the rights of all human beings anywhere and anytime.²⁷ Thus, Ladan succinctly points out that the cardinal characteristics and principles of human rights are Universality, Indivisibility and Equality of rights considered as human rights.²⁸

These rights are enshrined in international instruments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966), and the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (1981). In the context of armed conflict and terrorism, certain rights such as the right to life, protection from torture, and access to justice become particularly salient. While states may

derogate from certain rights during emergencies under international law, these derogations are limited, must be proportional, and must never affect non-derogable rights, for instance, (prohibition of torture). This framework is central to evaluating both *Boko Haram’s* conduct and the state’s response, especially where civilian rights are threatened.

➤ Defining Terrorism and its Human Rights Dimension

The concept of terrorism remains a subject of definitional controversy as a result of difficulty in finding a universally acceptable definition for it. The word ‘terrorism’ is etymologically from the word ‘terror’ which emerged in the parlance of English language to qualify the actions of the French revolutionaries against their domestic enemies around 1793-1794.²⁹ The difficulty is attributed to the fact that the concept is a political concept which is usually regulated through the instrument of the criminal law of

*Lecturer Departments of Public Law, Faculty of Law, University of Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria, Email; musaalkalilawan@gmail.com, Tel:+2347060757000

** Associate Professor, Faculty of Law, Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, Ondo State and Currently Chairman Ondo State Independent Electoral Commission, Akure, Nigeria; Email: aremsonjoe@gmail.com; joseph.aremo@elizadeuniversity.edu.ng; Tel: +2348038411128

***Lecturer Department of Sharia, Faculty of Law, University of Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria, Email; baakaka1400@unimaid.edu.ng baakaka1400@gmail.com, Tel: +2347078136255

****Lecturer Department of Sharia and Civil Law, Mohammed Goni Collage of Legal, Educational and Islamic Studies, Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria.

24 OHCHR, ‘Your Human Rights’ (United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commission) <<https://www.orchr.org/EN/pages/home.aspx>>accessed on 17/Oct/2025.

25 Ibid.

26 Louis Henkin, ‘The Universality of the Concept of Human Rights’ Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Sciences Nov. 1989

27 Ibid.

28 Ladan, M. T., Introduction to Jurisprudence: Classical and Islamic (Malthouse Press Limited 2010) 149.

29 Onikosi Ahmeed A. and Ahmed A. Muhammed-Mikaaeel, Legal Conundrum of Amnesty Grant as Mechanism for Combating Terrorism in Nigeria: Shari’ah Standpoint, (2023) Vol VIII, No. 1, Journal of Islamic and Comparative Laws, Unimaid, 30.

each state.³⁰ Therefore, each sovereign state has its respective laws regulating terrorism which also define the concept according to the political interest of its lawmakers. The United Security Council Resolution 1566 (2004) gives definition of terrorism as:

Criminal acts, including against civilians, committed with the intent of cause death or serious bodily injury or taking of hostages, with the purpose to provoke a state of terror in the general public or in a group of persons or particular persons, intimidate a population or compel a government or an international organization to do or abstain from doing any act.

On the other hand, the European Union defines terrorism for legal/official purposes in article 1 of the Framework Decision on Combating Terrorism (2002). This provides that terrorist offences are certain criminal offences set out in a list comprised largely of serious offences against persons and property which:

Give their nature or context, may seriously damage a country or an international organization where committed with the aim of: seriously intimidating a population; or unduly compelling a government or international organization to perform or

abstain from performing any act; or seriously destabilizing or destroying the fundamental political, constitutional, economic or social structures of a country or an international organization.

The United Kingdom's Terrorism Act 2000 defines terrorism to include an act "designed seriously to interfere with or seriously to disrupt an electronic system." An act of violence is not even necessary under this definition. United States has defined terrorism under the Federal Criminal Code, Titled 18 of the United States Code defines terrorism and lists the crimes associated with terrorism. In Section 2331 of Chapter 113 (B), defines terrorism as:

Activities that involve violent...or life threatening acts...that are a violation of the criminal laws of the United States or of any state and ...appear to be intended (i) to intimidate or coerce a civilian population, (ii) to influence the policy of a government by intimidation or coercion; or (iii) to affect the conduct of a government by mass destruction, assassination, or kidnapping; and---(C) occur primarily within the territorial jurisdiction of the United States...

The Arab Convention for the Suppression of Terrorism was adopted by the Council of Arab Ministers of the Interior and the Council

³⁰ Ibid.

of Arab Ministers of Justice in Cairo Egypt in 1998. Terrorism was defined in the Convention as:

Any act or threat of violence, whatever its motives or purposes, that occurs in the advancement of an individual or collective criminal agenda and seeking to sow panic among people, causing fear by harming them, or placing their lives, liberty or security in danger, or seeking to cause damage to the environment or to public or private installations or property or to occupying or seeking them, or seeking to jeopardize national resources.

In Nigeria, the word “terrorism” is not directly defined. However, an act of terrorism is defined in the Terrorism (Prevention and Prohibition) Act 2022. The Act defines an act of terrorism as “any act specified in Section 2 of this Act.”³¹ Section 2 (3) on the other hands provides that:

In this Act, “act of terrorism” means an act willfully performed with the intention of furthering an ideology whether political, religious, racial, or ethnic, and which-

- a. May seriously harm or damage a country or an international organization;
- b. Unduly compels a government or an international organization to perform or abstain from performing any act;
- c. Seriously intimidates a population;

- d. Seriously destabilizes or destroys the fundamental political, constitutional, economic or social structures of a country or an international organization;
- e. Influences a government or an international organization by intimidation or coercion;
- f. Violates the provisions of any international treaty or resolution to which Nigeria is a party, subject to the provisions of section 12 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999; and
- g. Any act willfully performed with the intention of advancing an ideology, whether political, religious, racial or ethnic, and which involves, causes or results in murder, kidnapping, destruction of government or public facility, seizure of any means of public transportation or conveyance of goods, dealing illegally with weapons (including explosives), and so on.

Generally, terrorism is of different types which include; state terrorism, religious terrorism, dissident terrorism, ideological terrorism, and international terrorism. State terrorism has been defined as acts of terrorism conducted by government or terrorism carried out directly by, or encouraged and funded by, an established government of a state (country) or terrorism practiced by a government against its own people or in support of international terrorism. State terrorism is as controversial a

³¹ Terrorism (Prevention and Prohibition) Act 2022, Section 99.

concept as that of terrorism itself, though not always, defined in terms of four characteristics (1) the threat or use of violence (2) a political objective, the desire to change the status quo (3) the intention to spread fear by committing spectacular public acts (4) the intention targeting civilians. This last element targeting civilians is problematic when one tries to distinguish state terrorism from other forms of state violence.³² However, where political or religious violence is used as a strategy of achieving certain religious goals, it is referred to as religious terrorism.³³ This form of terrorism is mostly influenced by religious extremism on the part of the adherences of a particular religion. A typical example of a religious terrorist group in Nigeria is *Boko Haram*. Dissident Terrorism also refers terrorism committed by non-state movements and groups against government's ethno-national groups, religious groups and other perceived enemies.³⁴ The impact of terrorism on Human rights is multifaceted, which have implications on direct violations by perpetrators for instance, killings, abductions, and torture, also indirect violations resulting from the state's militarized response, for example mass surveillance, arbitrary detentions, and militarization of aid. This dual threat models

is critical to assessing both *Boko Haram's* insurgency and the state's counterterrorism actions.

- **International Humanitarian Law (IHL) vs. International Human Rights Law (IHRL)**

In conflict zones like Northeastern Nigeria, both International Humanitarian Law IHL and International Human Rights Law IHRL are applicable. International Humanitarian Law or otherwise referred to as the Law of armed conflict may be defined as a set of rules which seeks for humanitarian reasons, limits the effect of armed conflict.³⁵ It is the body of international legislation that applies in situation of armed conflict.³⁶ It may also referred to as the body of treaty-based and customary international law aimed at protecting the individual in time of international or non-international armed conflict.³⁷ The objectives of IHL is to limit the suffering caused by war and armed conflict, prevent bloodshed and ultimately strengthen world security and by protecting the victims and participants in hostilities.³⁸ IHL codified in the Geneva Conventions, governs conduct during armed conflict, particularly the treatment of civilians and combatants. IHRL, by contrast applies at all

32 Royal B., Religious Terrorism (1990) 131
https://www.sagepub.com/sites/default/files/upm-binaries/33557_6pdf
accessed on 2/10/2025.

33 Ibid.

34 Martin G., Types of Terrorism in Martin G. (ed.) Development Next-Generation Countermeasures for Homeland Security Threat Prevention (IGI Global Publisher, 2017) 22.

35 Maurer, P. To Serve and Protect Human Rights and Humanitarian Law for Police and Security Forces (Geneva ICRC 2014) 372.

36 Solid GD, The Law of Armed Conflict: International Humanitarian Law in War, (UK, Cambridge University Press 2000) 23.

37 Ibid.

38 Nwachukwu, O. C, Armed Conflict under IHL: (2014) (5) Nnamdi Azikwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence, 36.

times, including during conflict, and governs the relationship between states and individuals. *Boko Haram* conflict is often classified as a non-international armed conflict (NIAC), the applicable law in non-international armed conflict distinguished two situations that in which the armed group has achieved a certain minimum control over a territory and that in which it has not. The applicable law depends on which situation holds.³⁹ In general; the following instruments of the law of armed conflict apply:

- a. Article 3 Common to the Geneva Convention 1949;
 - b. Article 4 of the Hague Convention of 1954 for the Protection of Cultural Property;
 - c. The Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons of 1980, its Protocols I-IV (though amended Article I) and Protocol IV;
 - d. The Ottawa Convention of 1997 Banning Antipersonnel Mines;
 - e. The Second Protocol of 1999 to the Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property;
 - f. The Optimal Protocol of 2000 to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflict;
 - g. Protocol III of 2005 Additional to the Geneva Convention.⁴⁰
- **The State Responsibility to Protect Civilians**

The obligation to secure human rights requires State Parties to take legislative, judicial, administrative, educative and other appropriate measures to fulfil their obligations.⁴¹ These positive obligations apply to all the rights and freedoms guaranteed by the relevant human rights instruments and must be fulfilled without discrimination.⁴² The protection of civilians is enshrined in International Humanitarian Law IHL particularly in the Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their Additional Protocols, which prohibit attacks on civilian persons and objects, demand distinction between combatants and non-combatants, and require human treatment of all non-combatant. The International Human Rights Law continue to apply during armed conflict, complementing IHL by ensuring rights to life, security, and dignity. Violations of these laws, such as indiscriminate attacks, forced displacement, and use of civilians as human shields, constitute war crimes under the Rome Statute of International Criminal Court (ICC). Under the principle of state responsibility, it is the state that bears the

³⁹ International Committee of Red Cross (ICRC) Advisory Service on International Humanitarian Law (2003), 2.

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ Human Rights Committee, General Comment no. 31.

⁴² Article 2 (1), ICCPR States that Each State Party...undertakes to respect and ensure to all individuals within its territory and jurisdiction the rights

recognised in the present Covenant, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.' The list of bases of discrimination is non-exhaustive. Other human rights treaties contain similar non-discrimination clauses. Article 1 IACHR is almost identical except for its references to 'economic, status' and 'any other social condition' instead of 'property' and 'other status.' Article 14 ECHR adds 'association with a national minority. Article 2 ACHPR refer to 'torture' instead of 'property'.

primary responsibility to protect its population from mass atrocities, including genocide, war crimes, ethnic cleansing, and crime against humanity. This obligation includes:

- a. Preventing violence against civilians,
- b. Prosecuting perpetrators of abuses,
- c. Ensuring humanitarian access, and
- d. Creating conditions for long-term peace and stability.

In case where the state is either unable or unwilling to fulfil this responsibility, this principle is not rendered void but rather triggers international mechanisms of protection. Recognizing the limitations of state-based protection, the international community unanimously endorsed the Responsibility to Protect (R2P) at the 2005 United Nations World Summit. R2P is structured around three foundational pillars:

- a. Each state has the responsibility to protect its population.
- b. The international community should assist states in fulfilling this duty.
- c. If a state manifestly fails to protect its population, the international community must be prepared to take collective action, in accordance with

the UN Charter, including coercive measures as a last resort.

R2P does not override sovereignty; rather, it reframes sovereignty as a responsibility, not merely a rights.

• **Securitization Theory**

Securitization theory posits that securitization happens when actors frame political agenda issues as existential threats through their discourse, prompting states to take action in response.⁴³ On the other hand, securitization theory shows us that national security policy is not a natural given, but carefully designated by politicians and decision-makers.⁴⁴ According to securitization theory, political issues be dealt with urgently when they have been labelled as dangerous; meaning threatening alarming and so on by a securitizing actor who has the social and institutional power to move the issue beyond politics. So security issues are not simply out there but rather must be articulated as problems by securitizing actors.

1. Meaning of *Boko Haram*

The term “*Boko Haram*” comes from the Hausa word *Boko* meaning (Book), and the Arabic word, *Haram* meaning forbidden.⁴⁵ It is a Hausa language nickname given by outsiders, meaning western education is forbidden in Islam.⁴⁶ One sect member said:

43 Caroline Cordeiro, V. S. and A. E. Pereira., Securitisation Theory and its Empirical Application: A Literature Review<
<https://www.scielo.br/j/rsocp/ast>> accessed on 25/10/2025.

44 Clara Eroukhanoff, Securitisation Theory: An Introduction E-International of Relations <https://www.e-ir-infor> accessed on 26/10/2025.

45 Daniel Egieba Agbiboa, *No Retreat, No Surrender: Understanding the Religious Terrorism of Boko Haram in Nigeria*, (2013) (2) African Study Monographs, 65-84. DOI: <<https://doi.org/10.14989/179136>> 4/6/2020, 10.

46 Alexander Thurston, *The Disease is Unbelief: Boko Haram's Religious and Political Worldviews*, (Published by Centre for Middle East Policy, Brookings, 2016), 6.

This appellation appeared first among the general public. On one side, that was a result of their difficulties in pronouncing the true name, and from another side it an appellation derived from what our scholars frequently mentioned in order to counsel people, especially parents and the students of institutions and universities, and the rest of those concerned with education...In any case we are dissatisfied with this appellation and we do not call ourselves by it. Calling us by it is a form of derisive nicknaming.⁴⁷

According to Halima, *Boko* means book, while *Haram* means bad so *Boko Haram* implies that learning at school is bad but they are really referring to Western Schools and not Arabic Schools.⁴⁸*Boko Haram* as roughly translated to mean Western education is forbidden; which was given to the group by outsiders based on their understanding of the budding set and its belief.⁴⁹ That translation *Boko Haram*, however, sacrifices some nuance and depth.⁵⁰*Haram* is an Islamic legal term designating a forbidden act.⁵¹

The sect opposes not only western education but also western culture and modern

science.⁵² It is an indigenous “*Salafist group*” which only turned itself into a *Salafist Jihadist* group in 2009.⁵³ The sect is a Nigerian Islamic fundamentalist group that seeks the imposition of Sharia Law in 12 Northern States of Nigeria.⁵⁴ Muhammad Yusuf, the founder of *Boko Haram* argued that Islam itself forbid Western-style education. Based on this conviction foreign, global colonialist schools have embraced matters that violate Islamic law, and it is forbidden to operate them, support them, study and teach in them.⁵⁵ The nomenclature, “*Boko Haram*” is a combination of the Hausa word, *Boko* (book), and *Haram* (forbidden). Put together, *Boko Haram* means “Western education is forbidden.” It is important here to clarify that the Hausa word “*Boko*,” originally had implications of “falseness” and duplicity.”⁵⁶ This certainly has increasingly become the case in recent times, but only with regard to books of Western provenances, as they were deemed to contain material antithetical to Islam and, therefore, “*Boko*.”⁵⁷ In any case, *Boko Haram* has even rejected the designation, “Western education is forbidden,” instead; the group now prefers

47Ibid.

48 Halima, C., *Meaning of Boko Haram*, (Guardian Newspaper, 14, October, 2014), 4.

49 Mike Smith, *Boko Haram: Inside Nigeria's Unholy War*. (I. B Tauris 2015), 19.

50Thurston Alexander, *The History of an African Jihadist Movement* (Princeton University Press 2018), 24.

51 Ibid.

52Ibid.

53 E. O. Innocent and J. Ibieta, The Cost of *Boko Haram* Activities in Nigeria, (2009) (2) (2) *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, (OMAN CHAPTER), 17.

54Ibid.

55 Muhammad Yusuf, *Hadhihi 'Aqidatunawa-Manhaj Da'watina*, (Maiduguri: Maktabat al-Ghuraba, 2009), 84.

56Agbibo Daniel Egiegba, (n65) 71.

57Ibid.

the slogan “Western culture is forbidden.”⁵⁸ The difference, as one senior member of *Boko Haram* noted, is that:

Boko Haram does not in any way mean “western Education is a sin” as the infidel media continue to portray us. *Boko Haram* actually means “Western Civilisation” is forbidden. The difference is that while the first gives the impression that we are opposed to formal education coming from the West, that is Europe, which is not true, the second affirms our believe in the supremacy of Islamic culture (not Education), for culture is broader, it includes education but not determined by Western Education. In this case we are talking of Western Ways of life which include: constitutional provision as it relates to, for instance the rights and privileges of Women, the idea of homosexuality, lesbianism, sanctions in

cases of terrible crimes like drug trafficking, rape of infants, multi-party democracy in an overwhelmingly Islamic country like Nigeria, pornographic films, prostitution, drinking beer and alcohol and many others that are opposed to Islamic civilisation.⁵⁹

The word *Boko* stood in for a system of ideas and institutions that the group not only rejected, but also considered diametrically opposed to the counter system represented by its version of Islam. Under Abubakar Shekau, the successor to Muhammad Yusuf after his demise, the group adopted the official Arabic name *Jama’atul Ahlul Sunnah Lidda’wati Wal Jihad*, meaning (People Committed to the Propagation of the Prophet’s Teachings and Jihad)⁶⁰ the term *Boko Haram*, implied a sense of rejection and “resistance to imposition of Western education and its system of colonial social organization, which replaced and degraded the earlier Islamic order of the *Jihadist* state.”⁶¹ Islamic scholars and clerics who once held sway in the caliphate state and courts assigned the name *Boko* to northern elites who spoke, acted, ruled and operated the state like their western

58Mantzikos Ioannis, The Absence of State in Northern Nigeria: The Case of *Boko Haram*, (2010) (7) (1) *African Renaissance*, 57-62.

59 Vanguard, “*Boko Haram* Resurrects, Declares Total Jihad,” (*Vanguard News* 14, 2009), 4. <<https://www.vanguardngr.com/2009/08/Boko-Haram-resurrects-declares-total-jihad>> accessed on 6/6/2020, 6.

60 *Ibid*.

61Isa Mohammed Kyari, *Militant Islamist Groups in Northern Nigeria*. In (*W. Okumu& A. Ikelegbe, (ed.) Militias, Rebels and Islamist Militants: Human Security and State Crises in Africa 2011*. (Institute for Security Studies, Pretoria, 2014), 33-340.

colonial masters.⁶² It is not uncommon to hear in discussions among Islamist scholars and average northerners that poverty and collapse of government can be blamed on the failures and corrupt attitudes of *yan Boko* (Modern elites trained at secular schools) who have acquired western education and are currently in positions of power. As such, the system represented by *yan Boko* is unjust, secular and has no divine origin. It is therefore, un-Islamic, which in turn accounts for its ineptitude and corruptness.⁶³

Boko is a tricky word to translate. One false etymology holds that the word is a corruption of the English “book.” Linguists, however, believe that *Boko* is an indigenous Hausa word.⁶⁴ Originally, it meant “Fraud,” “Sham,” or “inauthentic.”⁶⁵ It could be used as a verb meaning “doing anything to create an impression that one is better off, or that something is of better quality or larger in amount that is the case.”⁶⁶ *Boko* could mean “hoodwink”⁶⁷ During British colonial rule in northern Nigeria, this original meaning of *Boko* as “fraud” was attached to Western-Style schooling and to the Romanized script for writing Hausa, known as *Hausar Boko*.⁶⁸ Calling western –style education *Boko* connoted a feeling that colonial schools could

mislead Muslims into accepting false knowledge. In present day Northern Nigeria, some Muslims feel deep ambivalence toward western-style education. Such schooling is sometimes viewed with suspicious, but it is also recognized as a path to worldly success. More than just education is bound up in the word *Boko*.

The phrase ‘*Yan Boko*, where ‘*Yan* means “people; could be translated as representatives of western education.” People who have graduated from western style schools,⁶⁹ however, the phrase can have a broader connotation “people who operate within Western-Style frameworks and institutions” or “representatives of western culture” or even westernized people.” *Yan Boko* thus implies elites, who hold power because they can navigate western-style institutions.⁷⁰ It is just like western-style education, can simultaneously evoke suspicion and aspiration, so too can its products be both despised and admired.⁷¹ Put all these ideas together, and “*Boko Haram*” means something like western culture is forbidden by Islam” or the westernized elites and their way of doing things contradict Islam” not just in schools but also in politics and society.⁷² However, whatever the

62 Alexander Thurston, (n6) 23.

63 *Ibid.*

64 Alexander Thurston, (n6) 27

65 Paul Newman, “The Etymology of Hausa Boko,” *Mega-Chad Research Network*, 2013. <https://www.megatchad.net/publications/newman-2013-Etymology-of-Hausa-Boko.pdf>. Accessed on 6/6/2020, 2.

66 Alexander Thurston, (n6) 15.

67 *Ibid.*

68 *Ibid.*

69 *Ibid.*

70 *Ibid.*

71 *Ibid.*

72 Isa Mohammed Kyari, (n33) 11.

meaning connoted it still stand against westernization.

➤ Origin of *Boko Haram*

The precise date and circumstances under which the Islamist sect *Boko Haram* which is officially known as *Jama'atul Ahlis Sunnah Lidda'awati Wal-Jahad*, meaning (People Committed to the Propagation of the Prophet's Teachings and *Jihad*) emerged, still remains unclear.⁷³ However, *Boko Haram* is believed to have started as far back 1995 with the name '*Sahaba*' and it was led by one Abubakar Lawan.⁷⁴ The said Abubakar Lawan later travelled abroad to study at the University of Medina in Saudi Arabia, consequently leaving the old clerics to concede the group's leadership to a self-proclaimed Nigerian spiritual leader named, Mohammed Yusuf.⁷⁵ Yusuf was said to have abandoned the old cleric doctrines thus reorganizing and coming up with what became, *Boko Haram* in 2002 at the Northern city of Maiduguri where it headquarters was located.⁷⁶ In Maiduguri, Yusuf established a religious complex that included a mosque and a school where many poor families from across Northern Nigeria and from

neighbouring countries enrolled their children.⁷⁷

• Human Rights Violations by *Boko Haram*

Violation of human rights may also be the consequence of violent conflict. Conflicts have causes rooted in multi-faceted factors ultimately resulting in killing and displacement of civilians and gross systematic human rights violations.⁷⁸ Contemporary conflicts are regarded as the major cause of civilian death and suffering, as they employ deliberate targeting of civilians as the case with the *Boko Haram* insurgency. Some common human rights violations by the *Boko Haram* include extra-judicial killings, sexual violence, child recruitment, abduction, Rape, inhuman and degrading treatment, forced marriage as well as forced labour. It is appropriate here to discuss some of the human rights violations by the *Boko Haram*.

I. Extra-Judicial Killings:

Extra-judicial killings also known as extra-judicial execution is the killing of a person by government authorities or individuals without the sanction of any

73 Mohammed Kyari, 'The Message and Methods of *Boko Haram*' in Perouse de Montclos, M. (ed) *Boko Haram: Islamism, Politics, Security and the State in Nigeria*, West African Politics and Society Series (2014) (2) African Centre, Leiden and French Institute, Ibadan & Ahmadu Bello University, 10. Zaria. <[Hts://openaccess.eidenuniv.nl/.../ASC-075287668-3441-01pdf](https://openaccess.eidenuniv.nl/.../ASC-075287668-3441-01pdf)> accessed on 30/6/2020, 2.

74Cook David, "The Rise of *BokoHaram*," *As of February* 10, 2013. <<http://www.ctc.usma.edu/posts/the-rise-of-Boko-Haram-in-nigeria>> accessed on 30/6/2020, 27.

75EmmaUjah, el at, "YarAdua Orders Probe of *BokoHaram* Leaders' killing," (Vanguard Lagos, 4 August, 2009),8.

76 Ibid.

77 Mohammed Kyari, (n10) 13.

78C. L. Sriram, O. Martin-Ortega, J. Herman, *War, Conflict and Human Rights: Theory and Practice*, (Rutledge, 2017), 5.

judicial proceedings or legal process.⁷⁹ The rights to life is the most basic, most fundamental and the most primordial and supreme right which human beings are entitled to and without it the protection of all other rights becomes meaningless or less effective.⁸⁰ National and International laws recognise this right as accruing to every individual at birth. To this, the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) provided: Every person has a right to life, and no one shall be deprived intentionally of his life, save in execution of the sentence of a court in respect of a criminal offence of which he has been found guilty in Nigeria.⁸¹ Also, the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights recognised right to life as human right which are inviolable that, every human being shall be entitled to respect for his life and dignity of his person. No one may be arbitrary deprived of his life.⁸² While, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), is to the effect that, every human beings has the inherent right to life. This right shall be protected

by law. No one shall be arbitrary deprived of his right.⁸³

Despite the protection for the right to life accorded by the above instruments, cases of extra-judicial killings by *Boko Haram* is very rampant and alarming particularly in the North-eastern Nigeria, because the sect does not respect and recognises the above legal instruments. To this end the government sources in the states concerned have estimated that some 300, 000 civilians, including an undermined number of women and children have been killed by *Boko Haram* from 2009 to 2025.⁸⁴ The actual number of fatalities, however, is likely to be much higher, civilian have been shot, beheaded, amputated, stoned, drowned, burned and bombed.⁸⁵ *Boko Haram* has used stones, machetes, knives, sophisticated and high-calibre weapons, improvise explosive devices, and landmines, gun mounted on pickup trucks, armoured vehicles and motorcycles to perpetrate killings. Men and boys who refused to adopt the belief professed by *Boko Haram* are specifically targeted for killings, as were the law

79 CIRI, Human Rights Data Project, <https://www.humanrightsdata.org>> accessed on 21/10/2025.

80 Chukwu Amari Omeka, Rights to Life and to Dignity of Human Person (Sections 33 and 34 of the 1999 Constitution), Human Rights Law and Practice in Nigeria, Vol. 1 (Published by Chenglo Limited, 2005), 1.

81 CFRN, 1999 (as amended)

82 ACHPR, Article, 4.

83 ICCPR, Article, 6.

84 Global Centre for the Responsibility to Protect, Nigeria Population at Risk, 15 July, 2025, <https://www.globalr2p.org>> accessed on 22/10/2025.

85 Office of the High Commissioner on Human Rights (OHCHR), Report of the United Nations Commissioner on Human Rights Violations and Abuses Committed by *Boko Haram* and the Impact on Human Rights in the Affected Countries, <https://www.ohchr.org/.../HRC/A-HRC-30-67en.doc>> accessed on 22/10/2025.

enforcement officials.⁸⁶ Teachers, health care workers and members of civilian self-defence groups.⁸⁷ Office of the High Commissioner on Human Rights received for example, video footage of a massacre of civilians after *Boko Haram* captured Bama, in October 2014, it depicted men with their arms bound, driven in a truck to a bridge where they were shot, one after the other, in the back of the head and thrown into a river.⁸⁸

Boko Haram sect had executed women and girls especially those who were forced to marry *Boko Haram* fighters were executed when the group was forced to retreat by the Joint Military Task Forces, reportedly so that they would not marry 'infidels' or provide information to regional forces.⁸⁹ These acts are gross violations of right to life as guaranteed under section 33 (1) CFRN, 1999 as amended, Article 6 ICCPR, and Article 4 of the ACHPR. The relevant bodies tend to employ human rights law terms regarding the question of targeted killings and extra-judicial killings which have been condemned by all United Nations Bodies on several occasions, a prevent measures should be invoke in preventing loss of life in all circumstances.

II. Sexual Violence

Sexual violence is a serious violation of human rights and facilitates a range of other violations, which include, torture, enforced pregnancy among others, which is explicitly prohibited under the international, regional and national laws. Sexual violence has been defined as 'any sexual act or attempt to obtain a sexual act by violence or coercion, acts to traffic a person sexually regardless of the relationship of the victims.'⁹⁰ It occurs in times of peace and armed conflict situations, is widespread and is considered to be one of the most traumatic, pervasive, and most common human rights violations.⁹¹ On the other hand, the World Health Organisation (WHO) defined sexual violence as:

Any sexual act, attempt to obtain a sexual act, unwanted sexual comments or advances, or acts to traffic, or otherwise directed, against, a person's sexually using coercion, by any person regardless of their relationship to the victim, in setting, including

86 Ibid.

87 Ibid.

88 Ibid.

89 F. C. Onuoha and T. A. George, *Boko Haram's Use of Female Suicide Bombing* in Nigeria,

<https://www.studies.Aljazeera.net/.../20153189985734BokoHarams-female-pdf> accessed on 23/10/2025.

90 Carol Cohn, *Women and Wars* (1st Ed.) (Cambridge UK: Polity Press, 2010) 37.

91 Ibid,

but not limited to home and work.⁹²

The definition by WHO of sexual violence includes but not limited to rape, which is defined as physical force or otherwise coerced penetration of the vulva or anus using a penis, other parts or an object.⁹³ Sexual violence consists in a purposeful action of which the intention is often to inflict severe humiliation on the victims and diminish human dignity.⁹⁴ Also, the Rome Statute of International Criminal Court (ICC) has established in Article 7 (1) (g) that “rape, sexual slavery, enforced prostitution or any other form of sexual violence is further comparable gravity” constitute a crime against humanity.⁹⁵ Sexual violence is further explained in the international criminal court’s elements of crimes, which the court uses in its interpretation and application of Article 7. The elements of crime established that sexual violence is:

An act of sexual nature against one or more persons or caused such person or persons to engage in an act of sexual nature by force, or by threat of fear or coercion, such as that caused by fear of violence, duress, detention, psychological oppression or abuse of power,

92 United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, Sexual and Gender-Based Violence against Refugees, Returnees and Internally Displaced Persons: Guidelines and Prevention and Response, (2003) 43.

93 Ibid.

94 Carol Cohn, (n76)

against such person or persons or another person, or by taking advantage of a coercion environment or such person’s or persons incapacity to give genuine.⁹⁶

Sexual violence is committed for several reasons, sometimes ordered and or encouraged, sometimes with intent to kill, sometimes with intent to impregnate, sometimes on ethnic, racial, political or gender grounds, and always as an expression of power and contempt within a broader strategic content.⁹⁷ The perception of the position of women often somewhere between representing the property of the men, the sexual trophy exchangeable between male enemies a symbol of national and ethnic collectives and perceived unprotected civilians, shared common violence and anarchistic and discriminatory behavior, some of the sexual violence committed by *Boko Haram* fighters against women and girls is alarming. Human Rights Watch interviewed women and girls and documented eight cases of sexual violence perpetrated by *Boko Haram* combatants; most case of rape occurred after victims were

95 De Brouwer, L. M. Anne-Marie, Supranational Criminal Prosecution of Sexual Violence: The ICC and the Practice of the ICTY and ICTR, (Intersentia: Mortsel, 2005) 92.

96 Ibid.

97 H. Charles, and C. Chinkin, Argument: The Boundaries of International Law-Feminist Analysis, (2000), 152.

forced to marry.⁹⁸ Social workers with some of the victims in *Borno* and *Adamawa* states told Human Rights Watch that sexual violence of women and girls abducted by *Boko Haram* has been unreported because of culture of silence, and shamed around sexual abuse in Nigeria's conservative north.⁹⁹ However, victims of sexual violence face the risk of sexually transmitted infections (STIS). Many rape victims are infected with HIV and could be facing death due to the lack of adequate treatment against AIDS. The silence and stigma surrounding rape and sexual violence makes it very difficult for women to talk about their experience and to seek help. The mental health effect of sexual violence cannot be underestimated. They vary from anxiety, post-traumatic stress, and disorders to depression and even suicide, without appropriated treatment many women continue to live with the trauma inflicted upon them by the *Boko Haram*.

III. Abduction

The Report of the United Nations Commission for Human Rights on the abduction of children in Africa defines 'Abduction' as: ...the removal, seizure, apprehension, taking custody, detention or capture of an individual, temporarily or permanently by force, threat or deception for involvement in armed forces or armed groups for participation in hostilities, for sexual slavery and force labour.¹⁰⁰

98 Human Rights Watch, "The Terrible Weeks in Their Camp" *Boko Haram* Violence against Women and Girls in Northeast Nigeria, 2014 <https://www.hrw.org>> accessed on 22/10/2025.

99 Ibid.

Abduction of girls and women during armed conflict situation as that of *Boko Haram* occurs primarily for two purposes; their use in fighting forces and for physical and sexual labour.¹⁰¹ Girls or women abducted by fighting forces are often subjected to a number of human rights violations including being forced to kill sometimes family or community members; or participate in other taboo/violations as a means to break their link with, their family/community and hence lessen their desire to escape or who refuse orders are seriously beaten tortured, or killed. Girls may be subjected to sexual violation and be given to force commanders as forced wives, as can be seen by the *Boko Haram*, where in an interview a 15-year-old girl who was held in a *Boko Haram* camp for four weeks in 2013 described being forced to marry a militant more than her age. She stated that:

*After we were declared married I was ordered to live in his cave but I always managed to avoid him. He soon began to threaten me with a knife to have sex with him, and when I still refused he brought out his gun, warning that he would kill me if I shouted. He was huge man in his mid-30s and I had never had sex before. It was very painful and I cried bitterly because I was bleeding afterward.*¹⁰²

100 United Nations Commission for Human Rights, <https://www.daces.dds.un.org/doc/index> GEN/G06/163/PDF>

101 Ibid.

102 The Defence Post, *Boko Haram and the Chibok Abduction: Recognising and Addressing Grave Violations of Girls Human Rights*,

Also, on April 14, 2014 *Boko Haram* fighters abducted 276 young women from Girl Secondary School *Chibok*, in North-East Nigeria's *Borno* State. It was the incident that brought *Boko Haram* to global attention and with it, the movement's leader *Abubakar Shekau*.¹⁰³ Some 57 escaped in the night, jumping from vehicles, of the 219 held in captivity, 130 were shown in a video in May 2014, dressed in Hijab and reciting the Qur'an as *Shekau* taunted the Nigerian government, military and *Chibok* families.¹⁰⁴ On October, 2016 there was finally news for some with the release of a first group of 21 girls. A further 82 women were freed in May 2017.¹⁰⁵ Also, on 19th February 2018 at about 5: 30 pm 110 School girls aged 11-19 year old were abducted by the *Boko Haram* fighters from the Government Girls Science and Technical College (GGSTC) *Dapchi* which is located in *Bulabulin, Yunusari* Local Government area of *Yobe* State, in the Northeast part of Nigeria.¹⁰⁶ It was also reported that over 1,000 children were abducted by the *Boko Haram*.¹⁰⁷ Girls are abducted and trafficked to perform labour for the armed group within conflict zones, and they were also forced to serve the fighting groups like *Boko Haram* through cooking, cleaning, maintaining the camps and providing labour to support fighting groups, girls are forced to provide

labour in illicit operations where they cut down valuable timbers, or act as human mules carrying weapons, gems, drugs, and other goods.¹⁰⁸

IV. Torture and Other Ill-Treatments

The prohibition of torture and inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment is found in both International Humanitarian Law and International Human Rights Law. The prohibition is absolute in all circumstances and not restricted to armed conflict alone.¹⁰⁹ Torture is defined in Article 1 of the Convention against Torture 1984 (CAT) as:

*Any act which severe pain or suffering, whether physical or mental, is international inflicted on a person for such purposes as obtaining from him or a third person information or a confession, punishing him for an act he or a third person has committed, or intimidating or coercing him or a third person or for any reason based on discrimination of any kind, when such pain or suffering is inflicted by or at the instigation of or other persons acting in an official capacity. It does not include pain or suffering arising only from, inherent in or incidental to lawful sanction.*¹¹⁰

EGM/DUG/2006/EP, 12. <https://thedefencepost.com/2019/14/Boko-Haram-Chibok-abductions>> accessed on 18/3/2022, 4.

103 Ibid.

104 Ibid.

105 Ibid.

106 Premium Times, Boko Haram Attack, Kidnap off Dapchi Schoolgirls Occurred-Residents-School Staff,

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dapchi_schoolgirls_Kidnapping> accessed on 23/10/2025

107 Ibid.

108 Ibid.

109 Article 27, 32 of Geneva Convention, 1949

110 CAT, Article 1.

From the above definition it can be said that torture is the intentional infliction of severe mental or physical pain or suffering by or with the consent of the state authorities or otherwise in/on other persons for a specific purpose. From the foregoing it can be seen that torture has been prohibited Article 7 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights is very specific on the prohibition of torture. Nigeria, in compliance with the International obligation on the prohibition of torture, passed Anti Torture Act, 2017 into law by President Muhammad Buhari on December 29, 2017.¹¹¹ Prior to the coming into effect of the Act, there was no law in Nigeria whose sole objective is the prohibition and punishment of torture and other forms of ill-treatment.¹¹² Although, section 34 of the 1999 Constitution provides that: every individual is entitled to respect for the dignity of his person, and according, no person shall be subjected to torture or inhuman or degrading treatment'' the Constitution did not explicitly state that the freedom from torture is a non-derogable right.¹¹³ However, the Anti-Torture Act 2017 fills the existing legislative gaps by explicitly making the right to freedom from torture, inhuman and degrading treatment or punishment a non-derogable right, criminalizing torture and protecting victims and witnesses of torture.¹¹⁴ Section 1 of the

Act, imposes an obligation on government to ensure that all persons, including suspects, detainees and prisoners are respected at all times and that no person under investigation or held in custody is subjected to any form of physical or mental torture.¹¹⁵ Section 2 of the Act, clearly defines what amount to an act of torture as follows:

1. Torture is deemed committed when an act by which pain or suffering whether physical or mental, is intentionally inflicted on person;
2. Obtain information or confession from him or a third person;
3. Punish him for an act he or third person has committed or suspected of having committed; or
4. Intimidate or coerce him or third person for any reason based on discrimination of any kind.¹¹⁶

The section goes on to suggest torture does not include pain or suffering in compliance with lawful sanction.¹¹⁷ In the case of *Uzoukwu and 5 Ors v. Ezeonu II and 8 Ors*¹¹⁸ that torture could be brutalization of the human body or a mental torture in the sense of mental agony or mental worry. Torture is often used to punish, to obtain information or a confession, to take revenge on a person or persons or create terror and fear within a

111 Vanguard, Anti Torture Act, 2017: Issues, Implication for Police Officers, Vanguard, May 31, 2018, 5.

112 Ibid.

113 Ibid.

114 Ibid.

115 Anti-Torture Act, s. 1.

116 Ibid, s.2.

117 Ibid.

118 (1991) 6 NWLR (Pt. 200) 708.

population.¹¹⁹ From the above definition, inhuman treatment in the case of *Boko Haram* insurgencies may be illustrated as intimidation, pain, suffering or coercion on a person based on discrimination of ideology when such pain or suffering is inflicted at the instigation of an Imam or other person acting in such official capacity.¹²⁰ Instance where *Boko Haram* fighters executed male who refuses to submit to its ideology or intimidation and coercion by forcing young children to suicide bombings in public gatherings, including serious and credible threats as well as death threat to physical integrity of the victim of a third person, and prolonged incommunicado detention for instance the case of over 276 *Chibok and Dapchi* School girls. It is instructive to note that these acts amount to torture and inhuman treatments under the United Nations Resolution.¹²¹

V. Forced Marriage

The practice during armed conflicts of armed groups and forces abducting girls and young women and forcibly marrying them, as well as forcing parents to give them as wives in exchange for security is widespread.¹²² Forced marriage has only been recently charged within the International Courts as a crime. The elements of this crime, was developed within the recent jurisprudence.

The review of these elements will enable a more detail understanding the kind of violations suffered by girls subjected to forced marriage during situation of armed conflict as that of *Boko Haram*. In the case of *Prosecutor v Kvočka*¹²³ the Ad hoc International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY) was the first to recognised forced marriage as a prosecutable crime during period of armed conflict.

The office of the prosecutor (OTP) of the Special Court for Sierra Leone (SCSL) has presented the first clear argument regarding the crime of forced marriage, charging it as a crime against humanity.¹²⁴ The elements that the OTP of the SCSL raised in arguing the crime of forced marriage includes, sexual slavery which is carried out in a marital like union where the girls or woman is labelled as a wife, but in which the marital status is imposed by threat and or force. The OTP has also highlighted the diminishing capacity for the victims to leave the perpetrator i.e. husband, which includes for reasons of forced impregnation, forced child bearing, physical restraint or marking the identity of the victim as belonging to a particular group or captor. Strong feelings of culpability on the part of the victim if she was forced to commit atrocities, and abuse by the

119 B. Karumi and U. Alkali, *Torture as Violation of Human Rights: A Legal Dimension*, (2013) *Unimaid Journal of Public Law*, 343.

120 *Ibid.*

121 ICRC, *Basic Rules of the Geneva Conventions and their Additional Protocols*, Geneva: ICRC, 2206. 43.

122 Kristopher Carlson, *Forced Marriage During Armed Conflict in Northern Uganda, An analysis of Applicable International and Customary Law*, 2005.

123 IT-98-30/I-T International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY), 2 Nov. 2001. <<https://www.refworld.org/case/>>, ICTY, 4148117f2.html.> accessed on 20/9/2020, 1.

124 *Ibid.*

community members because of her past association with the fighting forced.

The OTP also stressed that in the aftermath of the conflict, the victim may continue to be linked to the perpetrators to a greater extent than would a survivor of sexual slavery, due in part to the imposed status as “wife.” Such imposed status may possibly prevent her from remarrying or it may play a key role in her family or community refusing to accept her back.¹²⁵

Boko Haram’s instances of forced marriage can best be appreciated on the interviews conducted by the Office of the High Commissioner on Human Rights (OHCHR) on the victims of forced marriage by the *Boko Haram*. One woman interviewed by the OHCHR stated that she had been coerced into marriage when *Boko Haram* attacked her village, adding that, they came back after killing the men and boys and told me that an imam in their group would preside over the marriage ceremony.¹²⁶ Also, OHCHR received reports of young girls being married off to fighters and older women forced to work as cooks and cleaners.¹²⁷ OHCHR documented cases of raped following forced marriages to *Boko Haram* members during an attack on *Bama*, in September 2014. Some 150 women at *Dalori* camp, which opened in April 2015 and hosts Internally Displaced

Persons (IDPs) from *Bama* had given birth after they escaped from captivity.¹²⁸

Furthermore, a 14-year-old girl informed OHCHR that when *Boko Haram* attacks *Damasak* in November 2014, after killing the men and boys, they took the women and children to house, and selected some 40 girls to marry their fighters. She was forcefully married and raped three times before escaping during a wedding with three other girls.¹²⁹ Also, Daily Trust reported that *Leah Sharibu* who was abducted by *Boko Haram* at *Dapchi* Secondary School was forcefully married to a *Boko Haram* commander who lives outside Nigeria.¹³⁰ The report also disclosed the information to the Newspaper that the said *Leah Sharibu* has delivered a baby to the *Boko Haram* commander in Niger Republic.¹³¹

CRITICAL EXAMINATION OF *BOKO HARAM* TERRORISM AND COUNTERTERRORISM IMPACT IN NORTHEAST NIGERIA

The critical examination of the *Boko Haram* Terrorism and Counterterrorism Impact in North-East Nigeria, can be examine under the following headings:

¹²⁵ *Ibid.*

¹²⁶ OHCHR Report, *Violations and Abuses committed by Boko Haram and the Impact on Human Rights in the Countries Affected*, (n.8-9).

¹²⁷ *Ibid.*

¹²⁸ *Ibid.*

¹²⁹ *Ibid.*

¹³⁰ Daily Trust, Leah Sharibu gives birth to a baby, <www.pulse.ng/news/local/leah-sharibu-reportedly-gives-birth-to-a-baby> accessed on 24/9/2020, 1.

¹³¹ *Ibid.*

a. The Dual Crisis: Terrorism and Counterterrorism as Threat to Human Rights

Terrorism is fundamentally an assault on human rights. It deliberately targets civilians to create fear, destabilize societies, and influence political outcomes. The impact of terrorism on Human rights is multifaceted, which have implications on direct violations by perpetrators for instance, killings, abductions, and torture, also indirect violations resulting from the state's militarized response, for example mass surveillance, arbitrary detentions, and militarization of aid. This dual threat models is critical to assessing both *Boko Haram's* insurgency and the state's counterterrorism actions. The reason behind the *Boko Haram* terrorism in Nigeria is strategically political in that the sect are attempting to replace the Nigerian state with an Islamic state governed by Sharia Law, especially in the Northern Nigeria Muslim dominated region.¹³² Sharia Law is based on the Qur'an which regulates both public and private conduct.¹³³ *Boko Haram* believes a strict Islamic state under Sharia Law would address the problems of corruption, bad governance, and western influence which does not meet the desires of the Muslim population.¹³⁴ Since its emergency, the terrorist group has employed all forms of guerrilla tactics and violence to

unleash mayhem against the state and people in an attempt to replace the Nigerian institutions, which they perceived as corrupt and western inclined. The violence unleash by *Boko Haram* on the Nigerian state is unprecedented in the history of insurgency or terrorism in the country. *Boko Haram* has used bombs to lunch attacks against government or western targets, to intimidate opponents and kill civilians.¹³⁵ Its fighters have slaughtered civilians during attacks on town and villages, assaulted and abducted teachers and students, abducted at least 2000 young women and girls and subjected many of them to forced marriage, forcibly recruited men and boys and burned and destroyed houses and schools.¹³⁶

The Federal Government of Nigeria in an efforts at resolving the security challenges which is term as terrorism, established and deployed Joint Task Force (JTF) to the terror-riddled states of Northeast Nigeria in what becomes one of the largest peace time military operation in Nigeria. However, the Nigerian government through the JTF's counter-terrorism operations has led to a document human rights violations, war crimes and possible crime against humanity committed by the JTF in their campaign against *Boko Haram*.¹³⁷ Report which was conducted by Amnesty International based on research and extensive field visits, more than

132 E. E. Aloba, and J. Inaku, and R. O. Ipuole, The Asymmetric Nature of Boko Haram Insurgecy and its Implications on Human Rights and International Humanitarian Laws, (2018) (3) (5) International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences, (IJELS), 882.

133 Ibid.

134 Ibid.

135 E. E. Aloba, and J. Inaku, and R. O. Ipuole, (n28).

136 Ibid.

137 Amnesty International, Star in their Shoulders Blood on the Hands, War Crimes Committed by the Nigerian Military.

412 interviews with victims, their relatives, eyewitnesses, human rights activists, doctors, journalists, lawyers, and military sources as well as analyses of hundreds of documents and more than 90 videos, revealed that not less than 7,000 people had die in military detention as a result of starvation, thirst, extreme overcrowding that led to the spread of diseases, torture and denial of medical assistance, as well as the use of fumigation chemicals in unventilated cells.¹³⁸ It was believed that about 20, 000 were arbitrary arrested, while about 4,000 were extra-judicially executed by the military, sometimes in collaboration with the Civilian Joint Task Force Member (CJTF).¹³⁹ This terrorism and the counter-terrorism activities and operation by *Boko Haram* and the Government have seriously impacted the human rights and international humanitarian laws and obligations imposed on both the actors to the hostilities.

The Failure of Human Rights Compliant in Counter-terrorism:

A human rights compliant approach would be balance security needs with obligations under international human rights and humanitarian law. In practice, however, Nigeria's counter-terrorism measures have often involved extra-judicial killings, arbitrary arrests, torture, mass detentions, sexual violence, and lack of

accountability. These violations have contributed to the persistence of the terrorism by *Boko Haram* rather than its resolution. It will be pertinent to examine some of the key human rights failure by the Nigerian Government in their counter-terrorism measures against the *Boko Haram*.

1. Extra-judicial Killings:

Extra-judicial killings also known as extra-judicial execution is the killing of a person by government authorities or individuals without the sanction of any judicial proceedings or legal process.¹⁴⁰ The rights to life is the most basic, most fundamental and the most primordial and supreme right which human beings are entitled to and without it the protection of all other rights becomes meaningless or less effective.¹⁴¹ National and International laws recognise this right as accruing to every individual at birth. To this, the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) provided: Every person has a right to life, and no one shall be deprived intentionally of his life, save in execution of the sentence of a court in respect of a criminal offence of which he has been found guilty in Nigeria.¹⁴² Also, the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights recognised right to life as human right which are inviolable that, every human being shall be entitled to respect for his life and dignity

138 Amnesty International Report
<https://www.amnesty.org/download/Document/AFR441662015ENGLISHpdf>
> accessed on 24/10/2025.

139 Ibid.

140 CIRI, Human Rights Data Project, <https://www.humanrightsdata.org/>
accessed on 21/10/2025.

141 Chukwu Amari Omeka, Rights to Life and to Dignity of Human Person (Sections 33 and 34 of the 1999 Constitution), Human Rights Law and Practice in Nigeria, Vol. 1 (Published by Chenglo Limited, 2005), 1.

142 CFRN, 1999 (as amended)

of his person. No one may be arbitrary deprived of his life.¹⁴³ While, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), is to the effect that, every human beings has the inherent right to life. This right shall be protected by law. No one shall be arbitrary deprived of his right.¹⁴⁴ Despite the protection accorded to rights to life by the international, regional and domestic instruments, reports from Amnesty International (2015-2022) document thousands of suspects' often young men and boys killed without trial or tortured to extract confessions. The death of Mohammed Yusuf itself epitomises this pattern, marking the beginning of the terrorisms violent escalation.

2. Mass Arbitrary Detention

All human beings have the right to enjoy their liberty and security, without an effective guarantee of the liberty and security of the human person, the protection of other individual rights becomes increasingly vulnerable and often illusory.¹⁴⁵ Yet, as it evidence by the most of the International Monitoring Organs, arrest and detention without responsible cause, and any effective remedies available to the victims concerned are

commonplace.¹⁴⁶ The Body of Principles for the Protection of All Persons under any Form of Detention or Imprisonment¹⁴⁷ defines detention as: 'Detained person' means any person deprived of personal liberty except as a result of conviction for an offence.¹⁴⁸ The term detention is therefore used normally for pre-sentence detention, while imprisonment is being used for post-sentence.¹⁴⁹ On the other hand, deprivation of liberty has been defined as: "Any form of detention or imprisonment or placement of a person in a public or private custodial setting, from which this person is not permitted to leave at will, by order of any judicial, administrative or other public authority".¹⁵⁰

Normally, in determining whether detention is 'legal or illegal' requires an analysis of conduct in the light of national law in force in that given country. Therefore, any detention of a person not in accordance with the law of the nation such detention would amount to illegal and arbitrary detention. In the course of such arbitrary and illegal deprivation of liberty, the detainees are frequently deprived of access to their families and lawyers and also subjected to torture and other forms of

143 ACHPR, Article, 4.

144 ICCPR, Article, 6.

145 Human Rights and Arrest, Pre-Trial Detention and Administrative Detention: Human Rights in the Administration of Justice, A Manual on Human Rights for Judges, Prosecutors and Lawyers.

146*Ibid.*

147 The Body of Principles for the Protection of All Persons under any Form of Detention or Imprisonment, UN. General Assembly Resolution A/RES/43/173, /1998.

148*Ibid.*

149*Ibid.*

150 Article II, of the UN. Rules for the Protection of Juveniles Deprived of their Liberty, (1999).

ill-treatment.¹⁵¹ Article 9 (1) of the ICCPR provides that:

Everyone has the right to liberty and security of person. No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest or detention. No one shall be deprived of his liberty except on such grounds and in accordance with such procedure as are established by law.¹⁵²

While, Article 6 of the ACHPR provides that: Every individual shall have the right to liberty and to the security of his person. No one may be deprived of his freedom except by law. In particular, no one may be arbitrarily arrested or detained. The above human rights treaties stipulated, though in a different term, that deprivation of liberty must be in all cases be carried out in accordance with the law. Deprivation of liberty must not be arbitrary; a wide nation was made possible for the international monitoring organs to consider factors that make the domestic laws or their application unreasonable in the circumstances. As to the principle of legality, the Human Rights

Committee has held that: It is violated if an individual is arrested or detained on grounds which are not clearly established in domestic legislation. In other words, the grounds for arrest and detention must be established by law.¹⁵³ The International Court of Justice (ICJ) has conferred significance weight to the ICCPR and its complementary treaty body, the Human Rights Committee (HRC), as standard bearing text of International Customary Law. Though not authoritative, the ICCPR is highly persuasive according to the ICJ. In the case of *Ahmadou Sadio Diallo Republic of Guinea v Democratic Republic of the Congo*¹⁵⁴ the Court applies great weight to the interpretation adopted by the HRC, since it was established specifically to supervise the application of ICCPR. The point here, the Court is to achieve the necessary clarity and the essential consistency of international law. By granting the HRC such persuasiveness in international customary law, the ICJ makes the ICCPR binding on states regardless of their membership status to the treaty.¹⁵⁵

151 See U.N. Doc. E/CAN.4/1999/63, Report of the Working Group on Arbitrary Detention.

152 Art, 9 (1) ICCPR.

153 Communication No. 702/1996, *C. McLawrence v Jamaica* (Views adopted on 18/July/1997), in UN. Doc. GAOR, A/55/40 (Vol II) 175, para 8.1

154 *Ahmadou Sadio Diallo Guinea v Congo* 30 November 2010, para 66-46 I.L.M. 712.< [https:// www.icj-ij.org/docket/files/103/16244.pdf](https://www.icj-ij.org/docket/files/103/16244.pdf)> accessed on 10/10/2020, 1.

155 The interpretation above is fully collaborated by the jurisprudence of the Human Rights Committee established by the Covenant to ensure compliance with that instrument by the States parties...since it was created, the Human

Rights Committee has built up a considerable body of interpretative case law, in particular through its findings in response to the individual communications which may be submitted to it in respect of State parties to the Optional Protocol, and in the form of its 'General Communications.' Although the Court is in no way obligated, in the exercise of its judicial functions, to model its own interpretation of the Covenant on that of the Committee, it believes that it should ascribe great weight to the interpretation adopted by this independent body that was established specifically to supervise the application of that treaty. The point here is to achieve the necessary clarity and the essential consistency of international law as well as legal security, to which both the individuals with guaranteed rights and the State obliged to comply with treaty obligations are entitled.

The international human rights law grants every person the right to be free from arbitrary or unlawful deprivation of liberty. This prohibition applies to all situations, including criminal proceedings, administrative detention, military detention, security detention, and detention under counter-terrorism measures.¹⁵⁶ Despite the above instruments of protecting arbitrary arrests and detention, it is pertinent to note that, over 20, 000 individuals have been detained in an inhuman condition in facilities such as Giwa Barracks and Maiduguri Prison, often without charge or access to legal counsel. Many detainees, including women and children, are held merely on suspicion of association with Boko Haram.

3. Sexual and Gender- Based Violence

Sexual violence is a serious violation of human rights and facilitates a range of other violations, which include, torture, enforced pregnancy among others, which is explicitly prohibited under the international, regional and national laws. Sexual violence has been defined as ‘‘any sexual act or attempt to obtain a sexual act by violence or coercion, acts to traffic a person sexually regardless of the relationship of the victims.’’¹⁵⁷ It occurs in times of peace and armed conflict

situations, is widespread and is considered to be one of the most traumatic, pervasive, and most common human rights violations.¹⁵⁸ The Nigerian Security Forces in their counter-terrorism measures were accused of rape and sexual exploitation of internally displaced women in exchange for food and aid. Such abuses violate Nigeria’s obligations under the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW).

4. Lack of Due Process and Accountability

The judicial system was largely failed to prosecute either *Boko Haram* suspects fairly or security personnel responsible for human rights violations. Military tribunals operate in secrecy, with little transparency or access to defense counsel. This impunity erodes public trust in the system. Furthermore, the Kanji trials of suspected *Boko Haram* members faced with procedural challenges such as lack of interpreters, insufficient time for the prosecutor to prepare for trials and for defendants to interact with their lawyers and limited number of trained judges.¹⁵⁹ There were only four trained judges assigned to adjudicate over 5,000 suspects. There was insufficient time given to conduct proper investigations and prosecutions. In general, the case proceedings were hurriedly conducted. Ideally, some of the challenges

156Fact Sheet No. 26, Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Rights of Anyone Deprived of their Liberty to bring proceedings before Court, Working Group on Arbitrary Detention, 3 OHCHR at para 9. <<https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/factsheet26en.pdf>> accessed on 13/10/2020, 1.

157 Carol Cohn, *Women and Wars* (1st Ed.) (Cambridge UK: Polity Press, 2010) 37.

158 Ibid,

159 Human Rights Watch, ‘‘Nigeria: Flawed Trials of Boko Haram Suspects’’ 17 September, 2018. <<https://www.hrw.org/news/2018/09/17/nigeria-flawed-trials-boko-haram-suspects>> accessed on 27/10/2025.

would have been minimized by the trials intended to hold in the Northeast rather than in the Northwest Nigeria.¹⁶⁰ This is in view of having access to the large number of *Boko Haram* suspects still in detention in the Northeast Nigeria, having access to witnesses, easy access to interpreters and ability to visit scene of crimes. However, there are still sporadic attacks in the Northeast which has resulted into the postponement of the trials of those suspects in detention.¹⁶¹

5. Securitization and the Suppression of Civil Liberties

Securitization theory which was developed by Barry Buza and Ole Waever in 1998¹⁶² provides a useful lens for understanding Nigeria's approach to the *Boko Haram* terrorism. The theory which posits that when political actors label an issue as a security threat, they move it beyond normal political debate, enabling the use of exceptional measures.¹⁶³ In Nigeria, political leaders and security agencies have consistently portrayed *Boko Haram* as an existential menace, legitimizing emergency powers and militarized governance in affected regions. For instance, the declaration of states of emergency in Northeastern states of *Borno, Yobe and Adamawa*, between 2013 and 2015.

These declarations empowered the military to conduct operations without normal judicial oversight. The Joint Task Force (JTF) and the Multinational Joint Task Force (MNJTF) were established to combat terrorisms but often operated outside civilian control. The operation of which had led to suppression of civil liberties. Reports by Human Rights Watch (2014)¹⁶⁴ and Amnesty International (2015) document widespread violations of human rights by Nigerian security forces in the Northeastern States of Nigeria, the violations including mass arrests, unlawful detention, and extra-judicial killings of suspected terrorists.¹⁶⁵ Many detainees were held incommunicado in military facilities under inhumane conditions, leading to thousands deaths.¹⁶⁶ Also, journalist and media houses reporting on *Boko Haram* operations have faced intimidation, censorship, and even arrests.¹⁶⁷ Furthermore, some of the operational measures put in place by the security agencies has seriously undermine the enjoyment of human rights by the citizens. Some of these operational measures include, curfew, roadblocks, and military checkpoints in the Northeast have restricted movement and economic activities.¹⁶⁸

160 Ibid.

161 Ibid.

162 B. Buza and O. Waever, *Security: A New Framework for Analysis*, (United State of America, Lynne Rienner Publishers, 1998) 16.

163 Ibid.

164 Human Rights Watch, World Report 2014: <Nigeria, <https://www.hrw.org/> accessed on 29/10/2025.

165 Amnesty International, Nigeria: Boko Haram and Nigerian Military Committing Crimes under International Law in North east Nigeria, <https://www.amnesty.org/> accessed on 5/11/2025

166 Ibid.

167 Ibid.

168 Ibid.

CONCLUSION

This paper has critically examined the complex relationship between terrorism and human rights within the context of *Boko Haram's* insurgency in Northeastern Nigeria. The analysis revealed that terrorism, as perpetrated by *Boko Haram*, has caused grave violations of fundamental human rights, including the right to life, dignity, freedom from torture, and gender equality. Acts such as extrajudicial killings, abductions, forced marriages, sexual violence demonstrate how terrorism directly undermines the moral and legal foundations of human rights.

However, the paper also identified that state responses though aimed at restoring security have in many cases replicated the very abuses they sought to eliminate. Counterterrorism operations, characterized by mass arrests, unlawful detentions, extrajudicial killings, and suppression of civil liberties, have deepened the human rights crisis. Thus dual violation underscores the paradox of Nigeria's counterterrorism framework; while designed to protect citizens, it often neglected human rights compliance, thereby perpetuating insecurity and public mistrust.

Drawing on securitization theory, the paper illustrated how the framing of *Boko Haram* as an existential threat has justified exceptional state measures and the militarization of governance, often at the expense of democratic accountability and civilian protection. The intersection between International Humanitarian Law and International Human Rights Law, further reveals that the Nigerian state retains the legal and moral responsibility to protect civilians even in times of armed conflict or

emergency. To this end, sustainable peace and security in Northeastern Nigeria require a shift from a purely militarized counterterrorism approach to one grounded in human rights protection, rule of law, and accountability. Addressing the root causes of extremism, poverty, corruption, marginalization, and poor governance is essential to preventing future radicalization. Only by balancing security imperatives with respect for human dignity can Nigeria overcome the dual crisis of terrorism and counterterrorism and uphold its obligations under international law.

The interpretation above is fully collaborated by the jurisprudence of the Human Rights Committee established by the Covenant to ensure compliance with that instrument by the States parties...since it was created, the Human Rights Committee has built up a considerable body of interpretative case law, in particular through its findings in response to the individual communications which may be submitted to it in respect of State parties to the Optional Protocol, and in the form of its 'General Communications.' Although the Court is in no way obligated, in the exercise of its judicial functions, to model its own interpretation of the Covenant on that of the Committee, it believes that it should ascribe great weight to the interpretation adopted by this independent body that was established specifically to supervise the application of that treaty. The point here is to achieve the necessary clarity and the essential consistency of international law as well as legal security, to which both the individuals with guaranteed rights and the State obliged to comply with treaty obligations are entitled.

Article 2 (1), ICCPR States that Each State Party...undertakes to respect and ensure to all individuals within its territory and jurisdiction the rights recognised in the present Covenant, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.' The list of bases of discrimination is non-exhaustive. Other human rights treaties contain similar non-discrimination clauses. Article 1 IACHR is almost identical except for its references to 'economic, status' and 'any other social condition' instead of 'property' and 'other status.' Article 14 ECHR adds 'association with a national minority. Article 2 ACHPR refer to 'torture' instead of 'property'.

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